

MOTHER LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODOLOGY IN PRIMARY CLASSES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8170511>

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Abstract

Currently, in our country, great attention is paid to the development of the mother tongue, and the use of various innovative and pedagogical technologies in teaching the mother tongue in schools and educational institutions is becoming a priority. This article is devoted to the methodology of teaching the mother tongue in primary grades.

Key words

scientificity, systematicity, consistency, consciousness, instructiveness, activity, principles of independence, development of creative thinking, text creation.

The mother tongue is the language of each people, nation, and nation. The vocabulary of the native language mainly consists of words and concepts that represent the life, culture and traditions of the people belonging to this language. The development of the mother tongue is inextricably linked with the social development of every nation, people and nation.

Requirements for student and teacher activity in lesson organization, management, and control, didactic rules are educational principles. These principles are explored in each discipline. Below we discuss the principles used in teaching mother tongue.

The principle of systematicity and consistency. The principle of systematicity and consistency plays an important role in teaching the Uzbek language. Studying the sections of language science in one order is consistent with this principle. In the teaching of mother tongue science, firstly, phonetics, lexis, and then word formation, word structure, morphology and syntax are given information. This means that the above principle is followed. It is also important to connect theory to practice in mother tongue teaching. For this purpose, every subject of phonetics and grammar should be passed in connection with orthography or punctuation, orthography or vocabulary. To implement this principle, it is necessary to take examples of grammatical rules from live speech, to use exercises that help students to develop creative thinking while strengthening the rules.

Consciousness also plays an important role in mother tongue teaching. The Consciousness Principle requires that students strive for conscious assimilation of a definition or rule:

1. Based on conscious verbal-cognitive education (OVKT) in teaching
2. To pay attention to the proportionality of the language material and the age psychology of learners.
3. To strengthen students' independent and creative observation skills
4. Conducting the lesson in a certain system
5. Paying attention to inter-subject communication
6. Strengthening speaking skills and increasing language sensitivity

The principle of independence and activity.

Through independence and activity, the student becomes an active participant in education. If conditions for independence are created, activity becomes the basis for education of independence. Organization of independent work in classes, management of the educational process based on the nature of the problems, questions and assignments, educates independence and activity in the young generation.

For this, the student needs to work independently and creatively in every lesson, to use the available opportunities of the language effectively, to increase his vocabulary, and to acquire the skills of speaking fluently and clearly.

The principle of scientificity and comprehensibility.

The principle of science requires teaching subjects to be presented on the basis of current scientific achievements. The principle of comprehensibility requires adapting the educational subject to children's age, personal characteristics, life experiences, and level of preparation. These two principles complement each other. When implementing these principles, attention should be paid to the following:

- teaching language levels in relation to each other;
- the teacher should be aware of science news;
- the teacher should express his whole opinion based on science;
- to distinguish between language and speech, to be consistent with concise and pronunciation standards;
- treating individual students individually.

The principle of directiveness.

Instructiveness is one of the means of increasing the knowledge of students and making the teacher's work more effective.

Visual aids can be used to provide new knowledge, to return what has been learned and to explain certain facts. Various tables, puzzles, educational tasks

aimed at accelerating the thinking process, computer programs, and audio-video educational programs can be used as an exhibition.

Specific principles of Uzbek language teaching

1. Observance of naturalness in language teaching.

Language teaching at school should be a natural continuation of the language acquisition process before school. When following the principle of naturalness in language teaching, it is necessary to take into account the knowledge acquired by students in primary school, to pay attention to teaching language materials in the structure of live speech.

2. Teaching written speech by mixing it with oral speech.

Teaching oral and written communication together will increase students' spelling literacy, they will be aware of the differences between orthographic and orthographic rules. Such teaching increases students' speech culture. This principle is implemented in the following ways: matching the sound with the letter, matching the punctuation with the tone, moving from the oral exercise to the written exercise.

3. The principle of developing students' speech culture.

Skills and abilities that serve to ensure the expressiveness and effectiveness of speech are formed in native language classes. All branches of the language also have a wide opportunity to develop speaking skills.

4. Separation of language sections and meanings expressed through them.

In order for students to master the language well, they need to know its phonetics thoroughly. Phonetic rules play an important role in determining pronunciation standards. Good teaching of phonetics also helps to teach spelling, lexicology and grammar well.

5. Forming the feeling of "language sensitivity" in students from a young age.

Thanks to this ability, students quickly read each word and form using their existing knowledge and skills and apply them to practical speech.

6. Continuous improvement of students' writing culture and literacy.

In order to improve students' knowledge of spelling and punctuation, oral and written speech should always be studied comparatively. For example, in order to put punctuation marks correctly, the reader needs to be able to understand the tone aspect of the speech in addition to knowing the syntactic structure of the sentence. By correctly determining the relationship between oral speech and written speech, students' writing skills will also improve.

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